

Comparative Study of Effects of Pneumoperitoneum on ETCO₂ and Hemodynamic Changes Before and after Insufflation of Peritoneum in Laparoscopic Surgeries in Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Laparoscopic surgeries often involve insufflation of the peritoneum to create a pneumoperitoneum, which can cause significant physiological changes. These include alterations in end-tidal carbon dioxide (ETCO₂) and hemodynamic parameters such as blood pressure and heart rate. This study compares these effects before and after insufflation, enhancing understanding of how pneumoperitoneum impacts patient safety during laparoscopic procedures.

Methods: Patients received a standard anesthetic technique with continuous monitoring (ECG, NIBP, Pulse Oximeter) recorded every 5 minutes. Premedication included ondansetron, glycopyrrolate, and midazolam. General anesthesia was administered, and baseline, intraoperative pulse rate, ECG, NIBP, SpO₂, and ETCO₂ were monitored. ETCO₂ values were recorded at baseline and intervals after pneumoperitoneum. Post-surgery, patients were reversed and extubated, with any complications related to pneumoperitoneum noted.

Results: Pneumoperitoneum leads to a significant increase in ETCO₂ levels. The rise in ETCO₂ is more pronounced at higher intra-abdominal pressures and with longer durations of insufflation. ETCO₂ levels gradually returned to baseline after the pneumoperitoneum was released. Pneumoperitoneum was associated with a significant increase in systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Heart rate also increases following the introduction of pneumoperitoneum. Mean arterial pressure (MAP) rises due to the combined effects of increased systolic and diastolic blood pressure.

Conclusions: Pneumoperitoneum has a significant impact on both respiratory and cardiovascular parameters during laparoscopic surgery. The introduction of pneumoperitoneum can lead to hypercapnia (increased ETCO₂) and a hypertensive response. The effects of pneumoperitoneum on ETCO₂ and hemodynamic parameters are generally transient, with a return to baseline levels after the pneumoperitoneum is released.

Keywords: Pneumoperitoneum, End Tidal CO₂ (ETCO₂), Laparoscopic surgeries.

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Introduction

Laparoscopy is a minimally invasive surgery allowing endoscopic access to the peritoneal cavity after insufflation of gas to create a space between the anterior abdominal wall and viscera for safe manipulation of instruments and organs. Hans Christian Jacobaeus of Sweden performed the first laparoscopic surgery on humans in 1910 [1]. The provision of better equipment and facilities with increased knowledge and understanding of anatomy and pathology has allowed the development of endoscopy for diagnostic and operative procedures. Laparoscopy was initially confined to gynecological surgeries in 1970. In late 1980 it was extended to laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Nowadays laparoscopy is used in colonic, gastric, splenic, hepatic, and urologic surgeries [2]. Reduction of post-operative pain and ileus, better cosmetic results, less hospital stay less

post-operative atelectasis, and wound infection are the advantages of laparoscopy.

Carbon dioxide is the most commonly used gas for pneumoperitoneum. Alternatives are helium, argon, nitrogen, oxygen, and nitrous oxide. CO₂ is superior because it is non-inflammable, inert, non-irritant, readily available, low cost, and cheap with a high blood gas partition coefficient (0.48) [3]. It is rapidly buffered in the blood by bicarbonate and excreted via the lungs. Absorption of CO₂ from the pressurized pneumoperitoneum causes clinically relevant cardiopulmonary and hemodynamic alteration. Carbon dioxide is 20 times more soluble than oxygen which is insufflated in a pressurized form at 10 to 12 mmHg. If the duration of surgery is prolonged, systemic absorption of carbon dioxide will be more [4]. Due to its high solubility, the incidence of gas embolism is rare. However, it is a

peritoneal irritant. The pneumoperitoneum and patient position required for laparoscopy induce pathophysiological changes that complicate anesthetic management. Therefore, to determine the adequacy of alveolar ventilation it is important to know PaCO₂ [3, 5].

Capnography constitutes a useful and non-invasive means of continuously measuring ETCO₂ which reflects the PaCO₂. In normal individuals, arterial and end-tidal carbon dioxide differences may vary from 2 to 5mmHg. The use of capnography monitoring can reliably and quantitatively provide vital respiratory parameters in intubated patients [6]. Alterations in cardiac output, distribution of pulmonary blood flow, and metabolic activity can also be reflected by the change in carbon dioxide concentration in expired gas. ASA mandates the use of capnography in all patients undergoing anesthesia [7]. The study aims to assess the effect of pneumoperitoneum on EtCO₂ and hemodynamic changes during laparoscopic surgeries in adults.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was done in the Department of Anesthesia, Osmania, General Hospital, Hyderabad from September 2020 to September 2022 after getting clearance from the ethical and scientific committee. Written consent was obtained from all the participants of the study after explaining the nature of the study in the vernacular language. This study was conducted on 80 patients of ASA I & II, between 20-50 years of age, posted for laparoscopic surgeries. Patients were counseled during the pre-anesthetic examination.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Elective laparoscopic surgeries
2. ASA grade I & II.
3. 20-50 years.
4. Both sexes.

Exclusion Criteria

1. The patient refused to participate voluntarily
2. Age less than 16years & more than 60 years of both genders
3. ASA III & IV
4. Advanced cardiac and respiratory complications.
5. Pre-existing systemic diseases.

A preoperative anesthetic assessment of patients was done. All routine investigations were carried out, and fitness was confirmed. On a preoperative night, each patient received a ranitidine tablet of 150 mg orally. All cases were done at Osmania General Hospital and after taking informed and written consent.

Pre-operative preparation: Fasting hours were 6 hours for solid foods and 2 hours for clear fluids.

Intraoperative Procedure: Patients in all groups received a standard anesthetic technique. An intravenous cannula was inserted after alcohol sterilization. Standard ASA monitors were connected (ECG, NIBP, pulse oximeter) and continuously displayed and recorded every 5 minutes till the end of surgery. All the patients were premedicated with Inj. Ondansetron 0.1-0.2mg/kg IV, Inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.2 mg IM 30 min before surgery, Inj. Midazolam 0.03 mg/kg IV was administered 2 min before induction. Conventional General Anesthesia was administered to all the patients. Baseline and intra-operative monitoring were done in the form of Pulse rate, ECG, NIBP, SPO₂, and ETCO₂. The Type of surgery was noted down and monitoring of ETCO₂ was done and values were recorded at baseline, 5 min after induction, and then 10, 20 and 30 min after pneumoperitonium. Then every hourly ETCO₂ was monitored up to the end of surgery and in the immediate post-operative period. Hemodynamic monitoring was done vigilantly throughout the surgery. At the end of the surgery, patients were reversed with Inj. Neostigmine 50µg/kg IV and Inj. Glycopyrrolate 10µg/kg IV and extubated when the criteria were fulfilled. Any complications related to carboperitonium, CO₂ insufflation, and laparoscopy were also noted.

Statistical analysis: All the available data was refined and uploaded to an MS Excel spreadsheet and analyzed by SPSS version 22 in Windows format. The continuous variables were represented as mean, standard deviation, and percentages. The categorical variables were calculated using the student's unpaired t-test for demographic data, changes in hemodynamic parameters, O₂ saturation, and EtCO₂. In all the above statistical tools the probability value i.e., P< 0.05 is considered as significant.

Results

Out of 80 cases included in the study the majority of subjects 47/80 (58.75%) were females. The male subjects were 33/80 (41.25%) in this study. Based on the age group distribution in the cases of the study we found that the majority in 31-40 years included 41/80 (51.25%) cases. The age group of 41 – 50 years included 22/80 (27.5%) cases. The least number of cases were from the age group 30 – 30 years 17/80 (21.25%) cases. The mean age of the study participants is 36.0 years with a standard deviation of 7.16. The mean duration of laparoscopic surgery in the cases of the study was 61.5 ± 5.8 minutes.

Table 1: Mean Systolic Blood pressure of the study subjects

SBP at different intervals	Mean SBP in mmHg	p-value
Baseline	110.4 ± 5.8	
5 min	112.2 ± 6.1	0.03
10 min	115.6 ± 7.2	<0.001
20 min	117.8 ± 5.3	<0.001
30 min	130.8 ± 6.8	<0.001
60 min	130.5 ± 9.8	<0.001
Post-Operative	120.8 ± 5.5	<0.01

Table 1 presents the mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) measurements taken at different time points during and after laparoscopic surgery. The baseline SBP was 110.4 mmHg. Systolic blood pressure significantly increased from baseline to 5 minutes post-surgery and continued to rise until 30 minutes. The highest SBP was recorded at 30 minutes post-surgery. After peaking at 30 minutes, SBP

gradually decreased, returning to a level close to baseline by the post-operative measurement. The initial slight decrease in SBP at 5 minutes is likely due to the effects of anesthesia and the surgical procedure. The significant increase in SBP from 10 minutes to 30 minutes post-surgery suggests a compensatory response to the surgical stress.

Table 2: Mean Diastolic Blood pressure of the study subjects

DBP at different Intervals	Mean DBP in mmHg	p-value
Baseline	82±4.2	
5 min	80.8±5.1	0.08
10 min	90.2±8.3	<0.01*
20 min	100.1±10.2	<0.01*
30 min	100.3±9.8	<0.001*
60 min	110.6±12.1	<0.001*
Post-Operative	88.5±4.9	<0.001*

Table 2 presents the mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) measurements taken at different time points during and after laparoscopic surgery. The baseline DBP was 82 mmHg. Diastolic blood pressure significantly increased from baseline to 5 minutes post-surgery and continued to rise until 60 minutes.

The highest DBP was recorded at 60 minutes post-surgery. After peaking at 60 minutes, DBP gradually decreased but remained elevated compared to baseline at the post-operative measurement.

Table 3: Mean Arterial Blood pressure of the study subjects

MAP at different Intervals	Mean MAP in mmHg	p-value
Baseline	75.7±3.9	
5 min	78.2±3.8	<0.001*
10 min	85.3±4.1	<0.001*
20 min	90.1±4.8	<0.001*
30 min	92.7±5.1	<0.001*
60 min	95.6±6.3	<0.001*
Post-Operative	80.1±3.2	<0.01*

*Significant

Table 3 presents the mean arterial blood pressure (MAP) measurements taken at different time points during and after laparoscopic surgery. The data includes measurements at baseline, 5 minutes, 10 minutes, 20 minutes, 30 minutes, 60 minutes, and post-operatively. The baseline MAP was 75.7 mmHg. Mean arterial blood pressure significantly

increased from baseline to 5 minutes post-surgery and continued to rise until 60 minutes. The highest MAP was recorded at 60 minutes post-surgery. After peaking at 60 minutes, MAP gradually decreased but remained elevated compared to baseline at the post-operative measurement.

Table 4: Mean heart rate of the study subjects

Heart Rate at different Intervals	Mean Heart Rate in beats per minute	p-value
Baseline	82.2±4.2	
5 min	83.1±5.5	0.241
10 min	88.5±5.8	<0.001*
20 min	90.2±6.2	<0.001*
30 min	100.1±6.8	<0.001*
60 min	110.2±8.1	<0.001*
Post-Operative	86±4.2	<0.01*

*Significant

Table 4 presents the mean heart rate measurements taken at different time points during and after laparoscopic surgery. The baseline heart rate was 82.2 beats per minute. Heart rate significantly increased from baseline to 5 minutes post-surgery and continued to rise until 60 minutes. The highest

heart rate was recorded at 60 minutes post-surgery. After peaking at 60 minutes, the heart rate gradually decreased but remained elevated compared to the baseline at the post-operative measurement.

Table 5: Mean saturation of the study subjects

SpO ₂	Mean SpO ₂	p-value
Baseline	99.1 ± 0.2	
5 min	99.0 ± 0.9	0.9
10 min	99.0± 0.8	0.37
20 min	98.7 ± 1.1	0.0012*
30 min	98.6 ± 1.3	<0.001*
60 min	99.0 ± 0.9	0.38
Post-Operative	99.2 ± 0.8	0.40

*Significant

Table 5 presents the mean oxygen saturation (SpO₂) measurements taken at different time points during and after laparoscopic surgery. The baseline SpO₂ was 99.1%. There were minimal changes in SpO₂ throughout the perioperative period, with

most measurements remaining above 98%. A slight decrease in SpO₂ was observed at 20 and 30 minutes post-surgery, but the values remained within the normal range. SpO₂ returned to baseline levels by the post-operative measurement.

Table 6: Mean ETCO₂ of the study subjects

ETCO ₂	Mean	p-value
Baseline	35.3 ± 1.1	
5 min	35.2 ± 0.9	0.08
10 min	36.1 ± 1.3	<0.001*
20 min	42.2 ± 1.5	<0.001*
30 min	45.5 ± 1.2	<0.001*
60 min	48.6 ± 1.8	<0.001*
Post-Operative	38.2 ± 0.8	<0.001*

*Significant

Table 6 presents the mean end-tidal carbon dioxide (ETCO₂) measurements taken at different time points during and after laparoscopic surgery. The baseline ETCO₂ was 35.3 mmHg. ETCO₂ significantly increased from baseline to 5 minutes post-surgery and continued to rise until 60 minutes. The highest ETCO₂ was recorded at 60 minutes post-surgery. After peaking at 60 minutes, ETCO₂ gradually decreased but remained elevated compared to baseline at the post-operative measurement.

Discussion

Laparoscopic surgery has many benefits for patients, including reduced postoperative pain and fewer wound-related complications. Generation of a pneumoperitoneum induces significant physiological changes which must be appreciated, and compensated for, to avoid adverse outcomes. Specific groups may benefit from laparoscopic techniques such as obese patients or individuals with severe respiratory disease. These factors all contribute to shorter in-patient stays and reduced perioperative morbidity. However, laparoscopic

surgery is not without its specific risks, either due to the risks associated with individual laparoscopic techniques or due to the physiological changes associated with the creation of a pneumoperitoneum. As a result, anesthetic techniques for laparoscopic surgery must be refined to anticipate these differences from open surgery. In the present study males were 41.25% and 58.75% were females. A similar study was done by Hussain et.al [8] where 50 consecutive ASA grade-1 patients were included. Of which 47 were females, 3 were males aged between 35 to 65 years who underwent laparoscopic surgery. In the present study, the age distribution was assessed. The majority of the study subjects (51%) were aged between 31 to 40 years. Subjects aged 20 to 30 were 21.25% and 27.5% were aged between 41 to 50 years. The mean age in this study was 36.01 ± 7.16 years. In the present study, the mean duration of surgery was 60 minutes with a standard deviation of 5.8 minutes.

Our study demonstrates that the intra-abdominal pressure created for laparoscopic surgery induces hemodynamic changes characterized by an increase in heart rate, mean arterial blood pressure, and peripheral vascular resistance. These extreme changes are seen in cardiopulmonary insufficiency patients. Similarly, Joris et al. [9] demonstrated during laparoscopic surgery, both mechanical and humoral factors contribute to an increase in systemic vascular resistance. He also explained that a decrease in cardiac output is caused by a reduction in venous return or increased systemic vascular resistance. It seems that the normal heart, which tolerates an increase of afterload very easily, becomes sensitive to changes in afterload like a compensated heart when this normal heart is subjected to pneumoperitoneum¹⁰. These results indicate the need for caution in patients with impaired cardiac function, anemia, or hypovolemia scheduled for laparoscopic surgery. These data suggest that it is prudent to reduce the rate of insufflation and limit abdominal inflating pressures to a minimum [10]. Also, V. Muralidhar et al. [11] studied the physiology of pneumoperitoneum and anesthesia in laparoscopic surgery. He postulated increased systemic vascular resistance, increased mean arterial pressure, and minimal increase in heart rate during pneumoperitoneum. In the present study, the mean SBP at baseline was 110.4 mm of Hg, and the mean SBP at 20 min was 117.8 of Hg with a p-value <0.001 , and post-operative it was 120.8.

There was a significant difference before and after insufflation with a p-value <0.0011 . In the present study, the mean DBP at baseline was 82 mm of Hg the mean DBP at 20 min was 100.1mm of Hg, and post-operative was 88.5mm of Hg. There was a significant difference before and after insufflation

with a p-value <0.00011 . In a study conducted by Hussain et al. [8] study 1, the systolic, diastolic, and mean arterial blood pressure increased from 12% to 17% of the baseline during CO₂ pneumoperitoneum at 13-15 mmHg intra-abdominal pressure.

In a study conducted by J G Mc Laughlin et al. [11] there was a statistically significant increase in systolic blood pressure (11.3%), and diastolic blood pressure (19.7%) from baseline values. Similar results were observed in other studies [12-14]. In the present study, the mean MAP at baseline was 75.7 mm of Hg with a standard deviation of 3.9 mm of Hg. The mean MAP at 20 min was 90.1 mm of Hg with a standard deviation of 4.8 mm of Hg and postoperative was 80.1 with a standard deviation of 3.2. The difference was significant ($p=0.004$). Similar results were observed in other studies [15]. In a study conducted by Rishimani et al. [12], physiological parameters at different IAPs were studied. MAP increased by 41.15% when high insufflating pressures were used. In the present study, the mean Heart rate at baseline was 82.2 bpm with a standard deviation of 4.2 bpm. The mean Heart rate at 20 min was 90.2 bpm with a standard deviation of 6.2 bpm and postoperative HR was 86 min with a standard deviation of 4.2 bpm. The difference was significant ($p<0.01$).

In the Hussain et.al study [8], the systolic, diastolic, and mean arterial blood pressure increased from 12% to 17% of the baseline during CO₂ pneumoperitoneum at 13-15 mmHg intra-abdominal pressure. In a study done by Umar et.al [15], in all three groups, the mean heart rate (baseline 84.08 ± 12.50 , 87.96 ± 15.73 , and 86.92 ± 17.00 respectively) increased during CO₂ insufflation and the rise in heart rate continued till insufflation after which it decreased and at 10 min after insufflation, the heart rates were comparable with the baseline. This significant increase in heart rate can be explained based on increased sympathetic stimulation and more compromised venous return in group III patients because of the high pressure of CO₂ used. Similar results were observed in other studies. In the present study, the saturation at baseline was 99.1% with a standard deviation of 2%. The mean saturation at 20 min was 98.7% with a standard deviation of 1.1% and post-operative was 99.2% with a standard deviation of 0.8%. The difference was not significant. In a similar study by Rishimani et al. [12] there were no significant changes in saturation similar to our study.

In the present study, ETCO₂ at baseline was 35.3mm of Hg with a standard deviation of 1.1 mm of Hg. The mean ETCO₂ at 20min was 42.2mm of Hg with a standard deviation of 1.5 mm of Hg and postoperative ETCO₂ was 38.2 mm of Hg with a standard deviation of 0.8 mm of Hg. The difference

was significant ($p < 0.001$). In the Hussain et.al [8], the end-tidal CO₂ (ETCO₂) levels increased to reach a plateau of 36 mmHg 20 minutes after the beginning of intra-abdominal CO₂ insufflation. The end-tidal CO₂ (ETCO₂) levels increased to 21 % of baseline (from 30 to 36 mmHg) during CO₂ pneumoperitoneum for laparoscopic surgery. In the Umar et.al [15] study, a comparison between 3 groups with different insufflation pressures showed a highly significant statistical difference in ETCO₂ immediately after insufflation and the same trend was seen till the completion of surgery and even baseline after insufflation [$p = 0.001$]. In the study conducted by Jadhav et al. [16] there was a significant progressive rise in PETCO₂ after CO₂ insufflation, with a peak at 30 min and thereafter plateau till the end of the procedure (avg. duration 45-60 min). Significant results were also observed by Baraka et al. [16] and other studies [17]. To prevent the development of complications during laparoscopy, sufficient monitoring and correct management are required. [18]

Conclusion

The pneumoperitoneum has a significant impact on both respiratory and cardiovascular parameters during laparoscopic surgery. Hypercapnia and Hypertension: The introduction of pneumoperitoneum can lead to hypercapnia (increased ETCO₂) and a hypertensive response. The effects of pneumoperitoneum on ETCO₂ and hemodynamic parameters are generally transient, with a return to baseline levels after the pneumoperitoneum is released. These findings highlight the importance of careful monitoring and management of respiratory and cardiovascular parameters during laparoscopic surgeries, especially those involving prolonged pneumoperitoneum.

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